

METHODS OF DETERMINING THE SAFETY AND ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACT OF DUST AND EXPLOSION PROCESSES IN MINING ENTERPRISES

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Abstract: One of the most important tasks of the enterprise is to ensure the safety of dust and explosion in the process of underground mining in mining enterprises. Mining enterprises departments of industrial safety and labor protection should be established. For example, the main method of preventing the explosion of coal dust located in the mine processing - they need to be processed with rock dust. Traditional methods of quality control of rock dust removal include and we can use radioisotope, optical and chemical methods. To implement them, the devices are environmentally equipped replaceable flasks with harmful radioactive elements, expensive optical sensors, desiccants, and chemical reagents are required. Compressed air is widely used in many fields as a safe technological energy carrier in economically developed countries, energy costs for the production and distribution of compressed air reach 10-15%. Analysis of industrial compressed air production and distribution systems sector indicates that the efficiency of the systems is relatively low. It's about not having enough attention is paid to these systems, because energy monitoring of compressed air systems has certain difficulties - the presence of complex and branched networks of air pipes with specific characteristics; low sensitivity of equipment that consumes compressed air; the complexity of inspecting pneumatic equipment, which is constant operation safety is ensured. The article analyzes the possibilities of reducing the cost of production and distribution of compressed air. The task is solved by hardware and software consists of monitoring and controlling the compressed air pressure at the main points of the network. The proposed method allows real-time detection of air currents occurring in the air duct network and sending commands for them to maintenance personnel. On the example of the Tebin Bulak mine, we considered the theories of analysis of the satisfactory approximation of the calculated air flow with the actual values. This is the practical significance of the obtained results that the developed method of monitoring the air flow in the network of air ducts is simple, it requires uncomplicated work.

Keywords: Risk of explosion in mines; coal mines; dust removal of rocks; thermogravimetry; thermogravimetric curve, compressed air, compressors, energy efficiency, air flow monitoring

Introduction

Development of coal mines is accompanied by intensive formation and release of dust particles into the atmosphere. Airborne dust is transported over long distances and accumulates both inside and outside excavations, which not only causes disruption. in the

mines operating conditions also create dust deposition exceeding the threshold values - the lower concentration limits of flame spread must be taken into account. In coal mines, an additional factor is created - it is necessary to identify limited areas that allow coal dust explosions to occur and spread. Conditional occurrence of dust explosion is a dangerous process. Thus, if no dust explosions were recorded during open pit mining high volume dust emissions followed by coal dust explosions have occurred in many coal-producing countries, including several mines. The issue of underground dust control and a large amount of data and research is available to assess and reduce the risk of explosions of dust-methane-air mixtures and associated worker injury in open pit coal mining processes. It is a mandatory regulatory requirement to ensure the dust and explosion-proof condition of mining operations, which is achieved by neutralizing explosive properties during coal mining. In most coal-mining countries, dust and explosion protection is the main method rock protection or rock dusting processes based on the use of non-combustible rock dust. Technical specifications" are based on limestone (dolomite) - substances with the basic chemical formula CaCO_3 . In coal mines, a type of stone dust with hydrophobic additives is used - stone hydrophobic. In mines engaged in intensive coal mining, several stages of rock dust application are carried out. Main after tunneling 10-20 m of mine deposits, the location of the rocks is carried out on the surface, then in the process of extraction, "secondary" and "fine reactive" dusting of rocks is carried out. Fine reactive rock dusting, in particular, was one of the first to be used in the coal mines of Australia. Rock dust removal is carried out using a wide range of pneumatic and mechanical devices. Practical experience shows that the use of rock dust does not have a significant negative effect and there are several theories on occupational health issues. The main components of rock dust (CaCO_3 and hydrophobic additives natural origin) are environmentally safe processes.

Picture 1. Coal dust explosion front panel "CDEM-1000" device 1 - power button; 2 - display; 3 - "enter" button; 4 and 5 - cursor up and down buttons; 6 - dust container; 7 - optical element.

Picture 2. Situations that cause the explosion of various gases and coal dust in the mine.

Existing technologies allow monitoring the parameters of various industrial systems objects and display them in a mnemonic diagram displayed on the operator's screen. More and more mining companies are starting to implement modern telecommunications solutions and technologies that significantly reduce the possibility of production errors and allow optimization the progress of production processes creates several opportunities. However, there are no existing approaches for real-time monitoring depends on the energy efficiency of the compressed air production and distribution systems. In many cases, single indicator of technical or operational problems characterizing compressed air systems causes an increase in the power consumption of the compressor station. The increase in energy consumption not only increases the efficiency of compressor devices and creates technical problems, this process but also occurs with uncontrolled air currents. Thus, a system that includes real-time mode should be used and monitoring of key technical parameters, waste compressed air detection procedures and rapid it will be effective for mining enterprises to implement a warning system to manage the elimination of the causes of wasteful air consumption. A review of the technical aspect of improving the energy efficiency of compressed air production and it is necessary to introduce distribution systems in mining enterprises. It is customary to divide compressed air systems into two parts: production and compressed air distribution processes. The first part includes the compressor units themselves, air filters, air and collectors, dryers, etc. The second part includes control valves, distribution air channels and including compressed air equipment and process equipment. The second part generally represents the external network of the compressor unit.

Discussion

The branching of the network of air ducts in mining enterprises and the large number of consumers of compressed air require strict consideration of the losses that occur during transportation. Available technical tools allow to control the main parameters and is seen as a carrier of energy at all stages of its movement. However, their widespread use is limited by them high cost and the need for additional maintenance costs. In some cases, special software is required, which is used as part of the necessary functional tasks. In our opinion, In such conditions, methods based on the observation of the main parameters of the energy carrier in real time, allowing monitoring of air flows in the mines and taking into account the factors, appear. To mining enterprises is considered a more appropriate process. Timely detection of

detected air currents can significantly reduce harmful substances and avoids losses and wasted costs in compressed air systems. The design of compressor stations and the calculation of air duct networks for stationary compressed design operating modes of compressed air consumers do not cause great difficulties. The main function of the compressor unit is to supply air and end user with relevant process parameters including pressure, flow and air considered as Important parameters of the external network of the compressor block are length, diameters pipelines and the presence of local resistance are considered. In the corresponding calculation and subsequent processes the selection of these parameters allows to minimize losses and use machines with the least compressors and opportunities to increase energy efficiency and energy efficiency.

Conclusion

The ventilation system in the mines should be fully developed. One of the methods of technical implementation of effective control of compressed air flow networks - software and hardware monitoring of air currents in overhead cable sections consists of real-time network-based monitoring. A mathematical model is formed that takes into account the characteristics and availability of air networks. The presence of pressure value indicators at the control points of the network makes it possible to determine air flows in the network and networks are formed according to the calculation method. Results of experimental studies in the air pipeline network on the example of the Tebin Bulak mine, the calculated parameters deviated from the actual values of air flow by no more than 9%. Implementation of this system precise energy service management reduces the electricity consumption of drives in developed countries, compressor units of mines are equal to 4000 kW/h per year. The software of this method allows real-time monitoring of the air duct network. In mining enterprises, various processes such as mining and loading and transportation of rocks are carried out. For example, I observed the first blasting processes at the Tebin Bulak mine. 521 detonators were detonated and I waited for heavy dust to rise in the mine. The dust spread over a great distance. Otelbayev Azizbek, a student of the Nukus Mining Institute under the Navoi State University of Mining and Technology, conducted many studies and researches about these mining enterprises. Azizbek has been conducting many studies on the activities of mining enterprises. Many of his articles have been published in international journals. Currently, Azizbek is conducting research on reducing the damage caused by blasting of dust in the atmosphere during open-pit mining processes.

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